

Okta for Good Nonprofit Technology Fellowship Application

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I am the Infrastructure and Contextualization Manager at MetaDocencia (<https://www.metadocencia.org/en/authors/irenevazano/>). I lead the organization's digital operations and technological infrastructure. My role includes supporting our open publication processes from an infrastructure perspective, ensuring secure and sustainable computational environments, and maintaining our website in collaboration with the team and community. I also oversee the design and optimization of the training, event registration, and certification systems while guiding the accessibility team to uphold best practices in inclusion, equity, and openness. From the infrastructure area, we design and implement workflow processes that must be accessible to our diverse community, often unfamiliar with the technology used for remote training and non-profit functioning.

As a librarian, I strongly emphasize open documentation and technical skills training for our non-technical team members and contributors to address the critical need for clear, up-to-date resources to support MetaDocencia's team and community in effectively advancing our mission. I started contributing to MetaDocencia as a volunteer in 2020 and gradually became its first full-time staff member this year.

What do you hope to accomplish through your participation in the Nonprofit Technology Fellowship?

Developing an efficient and friendly infrastructure for our contextualization-training-certification workflow has involved extensive design and documentation work. I have also been in charge of training and assisting our team in our daily operations. I have achieved this through easy-to-follow tutorials and guidelines. As our processes or technology evolve, this documentation requires frequent updating efforts to keep its efficacy and function as work guides for the teams and the community of practice.

By June 2023, when I started my position as infrastructure coordinator, there was an urgent need to have our processes well documented, and that they were documents easy to update by team members without GitHub knowledge. Due to the urgency and the end-user characteristics, I engineered a set of collaborative documents in the cloud that are open to other low-resourced, Spanish-speaking organizations to reuse and modify through Zenodo. I knew this system would scale poorly initially, but it was the best option in 2023. During this fellowship, I would like to bring this valuable body of fifty documents to an online platform that is easy to navigate, maintain, and open to everyone's contributions without technological barriers.

Describe a significant challenge or trend facing your industry today. How have you already been working as a leader to address it?

In organizations like MetaDocencia, the varying levels of digital literacy among contributors and the importance that everyone, regardless of their technical skills, can actively contribute to documenting and updating processes are both priorities and challenges.

Since 2023, I aimed to democratize our content and improve accessibility by implementing a dual system: editable documents in the cloud for internal collaboration and publication of finalized, non-editable documents on Zenodo with assigned DOIs. This approach balances inclusivity and transparency while ensuring the stability and accessibility of our documentation. We created detailed instructions and fostered an environment where all team members felt prepared to engage with digital tools, progressing on our mission to open knowledge and resources to others.

What specific deliverable or content piece do you envision creating during the fellowship, and how will it address this challenge or trend? (max. 200 words)

While the dual system (editable documents in the cloud and publication on Zenodo) implemented at MetaDocencia addressed critical needs in 2023, it revealed challenges in quality management, scalability, long-term maintenance, and comprehensive access. These issues include delays in updating public

documentation, difficulties providing cohesive access to documents, and barriers for contributors with varied digital literacy.

Through this fellowship, I aim to design a documentation system that bridges these gaps by converging the inclusivity of low-barrier tools with the scalability and robustness required for long-term use. Drawing inspiration from initiatives like The Turing Way (<https://book.the-turing-way.org/>), I will explore creating a centralized, dynamic, and accessible compendium that can adapt to our community's needs.

This system would empower contributors regardless of technical expertise, ensuring they can participate while maintaining high-quality, scalable, and reusable documentation. By integrating best practices from reference communities and aligning with the specific needs of Spanish-speaking organizations, this deliverable will enhance MetaDocencia's operations, serve as a model for fostering equitable and collaborative documentation practices across similar initiatives, and strengthen the foundation for knowledge-sharing and capacity-building in underrepresented communities.

Reflect on a specific professional development goal that you'd like to achieve during the fellowship. How will this goal enhance your effectiveness as a technologist and a leader?

Access to this fellowship will allow me to dedicate time to developing a centralized management tool for the rich and high-quality technology documentation created first in Spanish. In addition, following the FAIR principles of Open Science, these documents will be findable, accessible, easy-to-find, interoperable, and reusable.

I count on expertise to lead the selection of the platform, the workflow, and the implementation, which requires a thorough evaluation and validation process.

This project combines my expertise and passions: librarianship, infrastructure, and open science. I will use the lessons learned to serve low-resourced Spanish-speaking communities. At the end of this fellowship, I will develop my ability to democratize easy-to-follow documentation to the next level.

Project description

The Infrastructure area at MetaDocencia operates as a transversal space, supporting all organizational areas and all its contributors with highly variable technical skills (<https://www.metadocencia.org/en/equipo/>). We aim to open all our tools to empower other Spanish speakers in low-resourced regions to advance their missions. The main challenge we face is that we serve a highly diverse user base, with highly variable technology backgrounds, and we want everyone to be able to contribute to documenting processes.

In 2023, we started tackling this challenge through a combination of editable documents in the cloud and opening them via non-editable documents in Zenodo.

As the number of documents increased, this process presented several challenges:

- **Transparency:** As updates are first made in the cloud and later uploaded to Zenodo, this introduces delays in making the latest versions publicly accessible.
- **Comprehensive access:** Allowing the documentation to be consulted as an integrated whole rather than as isolated files linked only by hyperlinks.
- **Minimizing technological barriers:** Ensuring that the tools used to create, update, and consult documentation are accessible to all, require minimal technical skills, and offer a low learning curve.
- **Quality Management:** Ensuring that the documentation remains up-to-date and consistently high-quality can be a challenge, especially with a large volume of documents or multiple contributors.
- **Accessibility in Different Contexts:** Despite efforts to keep documentation accessible, differences in users' digital literacy levels can create barriers. It's crucial to consider the diversity of users' skills when designing access and navigation for the documentation.
- **Scalability:** As the documentation grows, the tools and methods for managing it need to scale without compromising quality or access. This

involves constantly reviewing the technological infrastructure used for storing and updating documents.

- Long-Term Maintenance: Although the documents are published on Zenodo with DOIs, the ongoing management and maintenance of the system for updating documents can be challenging, especially if the infrastructure is not frequently updated or adapted.
- Sustainability of Access: Ensuring that the infrastructure and resources required to maintain accessibility and update documentation are sustainable in the long term can be difficult, especially if they depend on limited resources or tools that are not universally adopted.

These efforts reflect our commitment to fostering openness and usability while enabling others to leverage our documentation for their projects and initiatives.

To share our experience with the entire community, following the philosophy of sharing knowledge and resources to foster a transparent, collaborative, and enriching environment.

Creating a robust documentation development process may interest small or medium-sized organizations that manage information, communication, and publication flows within a collective, open, and collaborative framework.

The scholarship will be a fundamental support to develop the following instances:

1. Design of a prototype that integrates existing documentation and ensures its centralized updating.
2. Analysis of available tools to manage the documentation compendium.
3. Collaborative and guided validation of the proposal. Testing.
4. Development of an implementation plan, including a timeline and workflow for implementation in 2026.
5. Launch the project progress report and present it to our work team and in open participation instances.

Following the example of reference communities such as The Turing Way (<https://book.the-turing-way.org/>), the centralization of documentation in a dynamic, accessible, and reusable compendium could make the resources developed available to the entire Spanish-speaking community, contributing to the development of capabilities and collaborations in the Spanish-speaking community.